

Interpreting Data in the Absence of Production Time Consistency and Source Tracking

Asier Zubia
TECNALIA, Basque Research
and Technology Alliance (BRTA)
Derio, Spain
asier.zubia@tecnalia.com

Laura Gomez
UPV/EHU
University of the Basque Country
Bilbao, Spain
lgomez063@ikasle.ehu.eus

Pablo Galan
TECNALIA, Basque Research
and Technology Alliance (BRTA)
Derio, Spain
pablo.galan@tecnalia.com

Arantza Bereciartua
TECNALIA, Basque Research
and Technology Alliance (BRTA)
Derio, Spain
ORCID:0000-0002-2147-2213

Mildred Puerto-Coy
TECNALIA, Basque Research
and Technology Alliance (BRTA)
Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain
ORCID:0000-0003-2616-3505

Abstract—Data analytics is providing data features to a large range of industrial processes that provides insights that extend well beyond traditional process control. However, data analytics has its own limitations particularly when confronted with challenges such as incomplete source traceability and random process-time window variation. In this context, robust data preparation emerges as a critical prerequisite for the successful deployment of AI-driven methodologies. This paper presents a structured approach to data preparation, following logic strategies applied to normally distributed datasets. The methodology is adapted to account for constraints such as limited data variability and process gradual drift, both presented in the glass bottles manufacturing.

Index Terms—Time variant manufacturing process, correlation, glass gob.

I. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing processes should maintain a controlled duration at each stage of the production line, with process parameters carefully recorded. Today, zero-defect manufacturing aims to ensure high-quality control and the traceability of each part, optimizing the use of resources and ensuring the quality of all manufactured components. In large-scale production of lightweight glass containers, manufacturing machines operate continuously, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, making it nearly impossible to maintain consistent operating conditions [11]. The process cannot be halted, and production can reach speeds of up to 800 bottles per minute, 48,000 per hour, and 1.1 million per day. Any quality issue can affect the production of thousands of bottles, but because the process cannot be stopped, it is continually tweaked along the manufacturing line. Additionally, in the glass container manufacturing process, generating an identifier for each product is neither necessary nor required by the customer, and unit-level identification of each bottle is not available, posing significant challenges to zero-defect manufacturing implementation strategies.

Horizon Europe (HEU) is the European Commission's key funding programme for research and innovation

References by [8] and [11] illustrates the glass manufacturing process in detail, covering specific improvements in the control of the gob process. In [3], the correlation between geometrical shape and gob viscosity is demonstrated; however, no details are provided regarding their influence on bottle quality. This paper summarizes the methodology followed to analyze the data aiming to establish data correlation between gob features and the glass distribution in the bottle, being the available data thickness measurements of the bottle in several control dimensions points.

The novelty of this paper is the finding of features within the available process data that allow to verify the intuition of experienced operators, which claim that the way in which a drop falls and its shape affect the bottle formation. The lack of industrial context for the glass sector adds to the major challenges in the data extraction of this pilot: (i) the lack of bottle identification, which prevents traceability between the gob and the final bottle it forms when inspected at the end of the line, and (ii) the absence of a fixed process time due to the annealing Lehr, where stresses are relieved after bottle manufacturing, and later, the presence of buffers in the cold-end area that result in a variable transit time of 40 to 75 minutes. The ultimate goal of this work is to study the effect of the gob on the total distribution of the glass, without the need to wait for inspection 40 to 75 minutes later, avoiding the manufacturing of defective bottles.

For insides into the importance of time process window, [2] emphasizes the necessity of measuring the process window as fundamental for establishing correlations between processing parameters, input workpiece material properties, and the quality of the resulting parts. Regarding pattern recognition in multivariate time series, [10] presents an automated event detection method based on several sliding time windows approaches.

To explain the nature of the aforementioned challenges, Section II provides an overview of the manufacturing process,

Fig. 1. Glass manufacturing line draw by Bucher Emhart [1]: bottle exits between 40 to 75 minutes.

emphasizing its complexity due to variable processing times. This section concludes with an introduction to the features of the gob.

Section III presents the methodology to estimate feature correlations and manage partial observations. In Section IV, this methodology is extended by introducing a grouping strategy that segments the dataset into meaningful categories, thereby uncovering stronger and more accurate correlations. Finally, Sections V and VI present the discussion and conclusions of this work.

II. CHALLENGES IN GLASS MANUFACTURING

Glass manufacturing cannot be halted easily because of the massive furnaces involved, Fig. (1) provides a schematic overview of the glass container manufacturing process. After preparation of raw material and melting of the material in a furnace at 1600°C , the delivery of the 1150°C hot glass gob and its loading into the mould is a critical procedure, and it is carried out through the furnace channel. The glass melted into the furnace needs to be transferred to the different moulding machines. This is done through the forehearth, which also condition the glass so that it reaches the moulding machines within the desired temperature and homogeneity range.

Machines can have up to 12 forming sections, with 1 to 4 cavities each (i.e., up to 48 moulds). While the bottles produced are marked with the mould number in which they were formed, usually by a dot code on the bottom following the DIN 6121 standard, the traceability of the gob at the time of cutting presents limitations. Specifically, while the gob is assigned to a forming cavity, the exact section it will fill is unknown during the cutting process in the data used for this study. However, after the forming process, the cold-end rotary inspection machines can read the mould's dot code using a light reflection system, linking the final thickness and quality measurements to the corresponding mould and cavity. For simplification, the system can be seen as 48 different machines, each with a specific gob input and a cavity with a bottle as output. However, after the hot release, the bottles

from each cavity are mixed, arriving at the quality inspection stage without any particular order, 40 to 75 minutes after forming.

A. Production and reaction time

A key factor in this loss of synchronization is the duration between the annealing zone and the inspection section at the end of the cold-end, typically ranging from 40 to 75 minutes. The delay is caused by several factors, like the opening and closing of accumulation buffers, operational stops and bottle breakage. Considering the variability of this time is crucial, as it impacts how production defects are detected and addressed. It is important to note that while defects may begin at a certain time—for instance, if a cavity starts producing defective containers at 10:00 AM due to a process variation—there is often a clear and gradual trend in the changes to bottle thickness. This is because the entire glass-forming process is highly stable, meaning defects typically do not appear abruptly. As a result, operators usually have ample time to detect and respond to such issues before they result in significant production losses. Even though it might take 40 minutes for defective bottles to reach the inspection machines, operators are able to act promptly once the trend is identified reducing the likelihood of prolonged defective production. For instance, even if the operator addresses the issue at 10:45 AM, any impact on production can often be mitigated well before the process stabilizes at around 11:25 AM.

Therefore, detecting a quality issue in a bottle caused by a gob falling outside the acceptable parameters (under the given manufacturing conditions) could save several hours of production. During this time, further production of similarly defective gobs would also be prevented.

B. Synchronising hot-end gob features with cold-end thickness measurements

Time series analysis is a statistical technique used to analyze data points obtained from consistent time intervals processes in order to detect patterns and trends. Since the current glass

process does not operate at consistent intervals, the analysis of the time window will divide the data in sliding windows, each 5 minutes (starting at 45 minutes, then 50 minutes... ultimately segmenting the entire dataset in 75 minutes interval windows). Each of these groups will exhibit cyclical and irregular characteristics, uncertainty in movement and patterns. Five-minute intervals were chosen because this temperature-controlled process experiences only gradual drift. Since the conditions change slowly over time, sampling every five minutes is sufficient to monitor any variations

During production, each bottle travels through the annealing lehr before it is gauged at the cold-end. The residence time in the lehr is not constant: typical installations quote 30–60 minutes for standard ware, and on our line the buffer upstream of the cold-end gauge extends this to anywhere between 45 and 75 minutes. The wall-thickness record taken at the cold-end at time t does not correspond to the gob whose geometric features were captured at the hot end at the same clock time t , but rather to a gob produced an (unknown) lag $\tau \in [45, 75]$ minutes earlier. Correct cause–effect analysis therefore hinges on an explicit time-lag synchronisation step [12].

Let $G(t)$ denote a vector of gob characteristics sampled immediately after shear (length, tilt, velocity, etc.) and $T(t)$ the mean side-wall thickness measured on the finished container. We aggregate both series in non-overlapping 5-minutes windows, producing sequences $\{G_k\}$ and $\{T_k\}$ with a common index k ($k = 1, 2, \dots$).

For each candidate lag

$$\tau \in \{45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75\} \text{ minutes,}$$

we align G_k with the thickness window $T_{k+\tau/5}$ and compute the Pearson cross-correlation

$$C(\tau) = \text{corr}(G_k, T_{k+\tau/5}).$$

C. Gob features

In the container moulding process, the molten glass is cut into preforms known as gobs at the upper part of the machine. This takes place in the feeder, which is the final section of the forehearth. The feeder consists of a cylindrical spout that rotates to maintain the glass at optimal conditions for forming. Plungers move up and down within the feeder to push the glass through orifices, after which shear blades cut the glass into gobs.

The performance of the gob formation process is monitored by measuring gob velocity and recording the gob’s fall using a high-speed camera (gob scan). A well-formed gob maintains a vertical alignment when entering the mould and does not tip to one side.

Fig. (2) introduces the main features studied in a gob shape analysis. As demonstrated by [3], changes in the geometry of the molten gob are correlated with its viscosity, this indicates that, beyond operator experience, gob shape plays a significant role in the forming process.

In this work, the gob parameters included in the correlation study are: a) Length, b) Diameter, c) Curvature, d) Tilt

Fig. 2. Main gob features: symmetry, tilt, length, speed, volume and shape.

(Degrees between the vertical axis and the main diagonal circumscribing the region), e) Volume, f) Weight and g) Speed. All these variables are measured for each unitary gob. The control system aims to keep the gob in a more concentric and vertical position, and with less residual stress into the moulds.

III. METHODOLOGY TO ESTIMATE FEATURES CORRELATIONS

In [11], Kovacec demonstrated that temperature control and gob mass were essential to maintain manufacturing conditions. However, it clarifies that quality depends on a large number of factors, such as: wear of the tools (mould, blank mould, plunger), dosing feeder (orifice ring, ceramic tube, plungers), sensors status and calibrations, glass containers producing machine (gob feeding, machine operation adjustments, tools lubrication), machine operator (replacement of worn-out tools, blank mould and neck ring lubrication), etc. Producing high-quality glass containers requires the precise adjustment of a wide range of parameters in both the furnace and the bottle-forming machine. Based on workers know-how and experience, certain gob parameters appear to influence the final distribution of glass in the bottle, it is an effect this study aimed to confirm.

A. Managing Data Drift in Continuous Glass-Bottle Production

Drift management—addressing the continuous evolution of data patterns over time—is essential for the problem we are evaluating. In manufacturing environment data distribution can shift by up 47.2% due to equipment wear and environmental variations, affecting significantly feature extraction for predictive models [4]. Covariate shift in glass industry evolves while maintaining fundamental process relations ships. In a process maintained 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, without interruptions, a gradual drift evolution presents large challenges. In [4], [6] and [5], different concept drift patterns

Fig. 3. Gradual drift of bottle thickness in specific dimension, the same gob can produce different thickness and different gobs can produce the same thickness.

were analyzed. Sliding windows approaches have demonstrated good results for maritime applications, for example a 48 hour sliding window with 6-hours incremental updates demonstrated improvements in retraining a model instead to fixed-interval retraining [7]. An interesting discussion about how drift is an early indicator of asset degradation and how the expert knowledge serves as foundation to anticipate breakdowns by Chapelin [9]. For most of the analysis summarized in this paper, fundamental insights from expert knowledge have been included [3], however, the data focused on gob characteristics show that different gob profiles can result in the same quality indicators in the final bottle, while identical gob features can lead to varying glass thicknesses (Fig.3). It is due to the process gradual drift and probably to missing factors in the data, such as temperature in the moulds or others. Process drift further underscores the importance of accurately identifying the time windows during which the process can be reliably analyzed and valid correlations between variables can be established.

How a future model can adapt to changing conditions variables of the process should be considered in the future. Drift detection methods and retraining strategies cover as well a large field in the SoA.

B. Data Completeness

The raw dataset comprised $N_{\text{gob}} = 2,545,368$ gob observations and $N_{\text{bottle}} = 2,514,861$ thickness records collected over five consecutive production days. Across the logged variables, the proportion of missing values was **below 2%**, well under the threshold commonly for ignorable missingness in industrial time-series of this magnitude. Consequently, we opted for listwise deletion, discarding any time-step in which any variable was absent. The final analysis table retained 2514861 aligned time-steps, which we judged sufficient for robust inference.

C. Exploratory Correlation Matrix

Pairwise linear and rank-based associations between each gob feature and the final bottle-base thickness were quantified using Pearson's r , Spearman's ρ and Kendall's τ statistics

[14] [15] [16]. Pearson cross-correlation descriptor indicates a linear relation between variables (assuming normal distribution), Spearman indicates the strength and direction of a monotonic relationship between two variables, but it is non assuming normal distribution and can detect nonlinear, but still monotonic relations. Finally, Kendall correlation coefficient could cover small datasets with non-parametric data.

Among the three cross-correlation descriptors, only the Tilt feature showed a moderate correlation with MIN1 (Pearson's $r = 0.63$, Spearman's $\rho = 0.59$ and Kendall's $\tau = 0.42$). None of the other gob features showed meaningful correlations with any other bottle quality indicators.

These findings motivate a deeper causal investigation, presented later in Section IV, rather than immediate direct control-law derivation.

D. Planned Causal Testing

While correlation offers first-order evidence of statistical association, it does not establish process causality. To that end, we apply multivariate Granger-causality analysis on the synchronised cavity-level time-series, using lags of 40–75 minutes, the residence-time range measured between gob information and inspection. The detailed methodology is referred in the next section, where the lag-optimisation is discussed in concert with the sliding-window procedure. Granger causality was selected because it explicitly tests whether lagged gob features add predictive power beyond an autoregressive thickness baseline. Here we simply note that Granger testing provides a rigorous framework to decide whether past gob features help predict future thickness beyond autoregressive baselines.

IV. LAG-OPTIMISED TIME-WINDOW ANALYSIS

Obtaining the necessary data for this analysis proved challenging due to the high stability of the glass manufacturing process. Identifying periods where the bottle thickness exhibited a notable trend was essential as these trends were crucial for the analysis. To address this, we focused on a specific time frame where such trends could be observed. We therefore formulated the problem as a discrete optimisation of a sliding-window discrepancy function $D(\tau)$ over the candidate lags $\tau \in \{40, 45, \dots, 75\}$ minutes. Let the aggregated gob series be (G_k) and the aggregated thickness series (T_k). For a candidate lag τ (expressed in five-minute units) we define the discrepancy function

$$D(\tau) = 1 - |\text{corr}(G_k, T_{k+\tau})|, \quad (1)$$

so that smaller (D) signifies stronger absolute correlation. The optimisation selects the lag $\tau^* = \arg \min_{\tau} D(\tau)$, i.e., the window that maximises the magnitude of the gob–thickness correlation.

The dataset used in this study encompasses five days of production data specific to a single mold design, as various molds are produced to meet client-specific requirements. This selection allowed us to isolate the impact of gob characteristics on bottle quality without the confounding variability introduced by mold differences.

Fig. 4. Procedure for estimation the optimal range of manipulable variables.

The preprocessing of the data involved several complex steps. Since we only had gob parameters related to the gob (A, B, C, etc.), while the final bottle thickness data included both section and cavity information (e.g., 1A, 3B, etc.), we implemented two distinct preprocessing approaches to gain different perspectives:

- **Cavity-level Grouping:** In this approach, gob features were grouped by cavity, and the same was done for the thickness measurements. This allowed for a statistically sound analysis of gob characteristics and bottle thickness at the cavity level.
- **Cavity and Section-level Grouping:** Here, gob features were still grouped by cavity, but the thickness measurements were grouped by both cavity and section, providing a more granular level of analysis since we had access to both attributes for the thickness data.

After grouping the data, the gob characteristics were aggregated every 5 minutes, calculating the mean, median, and standard deviation for each cavity. Thickness values were treated with the same 5-minute resolution. For the final glass distribution, we focus on one indicator which corresponds to the bottle base — the most critical measurement for this production because it lies closest to the rejection limit, it is called MIN1.

Once the data was aggregated, the next step was synchronizing the gob feature data with the bottle thickness data based on the annealing time. Since bottles can take anywhere between 40 and 75 minutes to move from the moulding machine to the

Fig. 5. The data set was analyzed as a time series. Sliding time windows were calculated after ensuring a synchronization event along the variables analyzed for this study.

inspection station, the gob data was aligned with the thickness measurements from 40 to 75 minutes later every 5 minutes. A sliding window segmentation has been implemented by moving a fixed sized window over the time series, defining a discrepancy measure in defined segments. The analysis tried to identify windows that contain dissimilar segments being the peak of the discrepancy functions the references for changes.

Through analysis, it was determined that the optimal synchronization window was 45 minutes. Therefore, all subsequent analyses and conclusions are based on a 45-minute delay between gob formation and bottle inspection.

This approach allowed us to explore correlations between gob features and bottle quality across multiple dimensions.

The following sections will present the detailed analyses and results based on these datasets.

A. Correlation and Causality Tests

To examine the relationship between various gob characteristics and the final glass bottle thickness, measured as MIN1, we computed several correlation test: the Pearson correlation, Granger causality test and ANOVA. Only Granger test obtained significant results as it has due to the own manufacturing process.

Pearson and Spearman correlations were computed between each of the gob descriptors and MIN1 and Tilt shows the strongest magnitude.

B. Granger Causality Test

Granger causality is a statistical concept that determines whether one time series can be useful in predicting another (2). A variable X is said to Granger-cause Y if past values of X provide statistically significant information about future values of Y that is not contained in past values of Y alone. The test is based on the following regression model:

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_i Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i X_{t-i} + \epsilon_t, \quad (2)$$

where (p) is the maximum number of lagged observations (maximum lag length).

Focusing on the 45-minute time difference, which showed the strongest correlations in our previous analysis, we conducted Granger causality tests with a maximum lag of 15 to examine the potential causal relationship between Tilt and MIN1 in Cavity A. The results suggest possible temporal dependencies between these variables, as the null hypothesis of no Granger causality was rejected for most of the tested lags. This indicates that past values of Tilt might contain information that could be valuable in predicting future values of MIN1. The varying strength of these possible temporal relationships across different lags suggests a complex underlying structure in the manufacturing process dynamics. These findings point to the possibility that the relationship between Tilt and MIN1 at the 40-minute time difference extends beyond mere correlation, though further investigation would be needed to establish definitive causal links.

C. ANOVA

The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests the null hypothesis that the means of k independent groups are equal. To apply ANOVA, the input parameters—such as gob characteristics—should be uniformly distributed, with MIN1 defined as the dependent variable. In this case, the data do not fully represent the entire variability of the experimental space. However, since the data come from actual production, such full variability may not be present. Despite the complexity of the dataset, ANOVA was still employed to identify statistically distinct groups.

Continuous predictors were discretised by three specific interval groups (Length: low / medium / high) or two in the

case of Tilt (Tilt: low / high). Within each interval we collected the corresponding base-thickness measurements MIN1 and ran a separate ANOVA per predictor.

TABLE I
ONE-WAY ANOVA SUMMARY: GOB LENGTH VERSUS BASE THICKNESS (MIN1)

Statistic	Value
Grouping rule	Empirical terciles (low / medium / high)
Group means (mm)	1.536 / 1.558 / 1.522
ANOVA $F(2, 6954)$	80.62, $p = 2.4 \times 10^{-35}$
Partial η^2	0.023
Tukey HSD (mm, 95 CI)	High-Low: 0.014 (0.001, 0.022) High-Med: 0.036 (0.029, 0.044) Low-Med: 0.022 (0.016, 0.028)
Assumption checks	SW $p < 10^{-7}$; Levene $p < 10^{-15}$
Welch ANOVA	$F=76.4, (2,3245)$; $p < 10^{-30}$

Note. CI = confidence interval; SW = Shapiro-Wilk normality test.

TABLE II
ONE-WAY ANOVA SUMMARY: GOB TILT VERSUS BASE THICKNESS (MIN1)

Statistic	Value
Grouping rule	Median split (low / high)
Group means (mm)	1.577 / 1.518
ANOVA $F(1, 6951)$	768.95, $p = 1.29 \times 10^{-160}$
Partial η^2	0.10
Mean difference (mm, 95 CI)	0.058 (0.054, 0.062)
Assumption checks	SW $p < 10^{-13}$; Levene $p = 0.055$
Welch t -test	$t=-27.7 (5669)$; $p < 10^{-160}$

Both predictors exhibit statistically—and practically—significant effects on base thickness. Length shows a moderate effect ($\eta^2 = 0.02$); increasing the gob length from the medium to the high interval reduces MIN1 by 0.036 mm, pushing the product closer to the rejection limit. Tilt exerts a stronger influence ($\eta^2 = 0.10$); bottles originating from the high-tilt subset are on average 0.058 mm thinner at the base than those from the low-tilt subset. These magnitudes justify tightening process-control set-points for both variables.

V. GENERALIZATION AND DISCUSSION

This study suggests that data-driven, time-sensitive, and cavity-specific parameter tuning could serve as a practical model for quality control in glass manufacturing. The approach is designed to enable immediate identification and removal of defective bottles from the production line through an operator alarm system, offering a focused and scalable approach that could be extended to other continuous manufacturing environments.

However, the possible effect of the gob on how the glass is distributed throughout the mould has not been demonstrated, it can being blurred by variables that have greater importance. Currently, additional parameters in the gob, such as viscosity and temperature could be taken in the study, like in [3].

As previously mentioned, in the current data set, the gob is assigned to a forming cavity but the exact section it will fill is unknown during the cutting process. Although such traceability is technically feasible, it is not presently implemented. Enhancing traceability between the gob and the final bottle represents a promising avenue for improving process understanding and defect prediction. A two-month dataset of gob characteristics has been published on Zenodo [17].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to determine whether certain gob characteristics improve glass distribution in bottle forming. Through the application of various analytical methods, initial findings **suggested** that tilt and diameter may influence the thickness at the bottom of the bottle.

While these initial results provide promising insights, the current dataset has limitations that prevent definitive conclusions. To refine and validate the hypothesis, future work will involve the collection and analysis of more relevant and extensive data. This will enable a deeper research into the role of gob characteristics in determining bottle quality, ultimately leading to more precise control over the manufacturing process.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially supported by the HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01 openZDM project [13], under Grant Agreement No. 101058673. The paper reflects the authors' views, and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

REFERENCES

- [1] "Automation line for glass bottles manufacturing". Accessed: April, 1, 2025.[Online.] Available: <https://www.bucherindustries.com/en/divisions/bucher-emhart-glass>.
- [2] M. L. Cabrera, W. Zouhri, S. Zimmer-Chevret, and J-Y. Dantan. "An overview of strategies for identifying manufacturing process window through design of experiments and machine learning techniques while considering the uncertainty associated with". *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*. Springer Nature. Published: 20 September 2024. Vol 134, pages 4981–5019, 2024.
- [3] M. Hussain, M. O'Nils, J. Lundgren, and I. Shallari. "A Study on the Correlation between Change in the Geometrical Dimension of a Free-Falling Molten Glass Gob and Its Viscosity". *Sensors*. Vol 22. 661. 10.3390/s22020661. 2022.
- [4] S. Mannapur. "Understanding Data Drift and Concept Drift in Machine Learning Systems". *International Journal of Scientific Research in Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology*. Pages 318-330, vol 11. doi = 10.32628/CSEIT25111239. 2025.
- [5] R. Benni and S. Totad. "Impact analysis of real and virtual concept drifts on the predictive performance of classifiers". *Procedia Computer Science*. Volume 235, 2024.
- [6] J. Zenisek, F. Holzinger and M. Affenzeller. "Machine learning based concept drift detection for predictive maintenance". *Computers & Industrial Engineering*. Vol 137. 2019.
- [7] M. Casimiro, P. Romano, D. Garlan and L. Rodrigues. "Towards a Framework for Adapting Machine Learning Components". *IEEE International Conference on Autonomic Computing and Self-Organizing Systems (ACSOS)*. 2022.
- [8] K. Hiltmann and T. Neubauer. "Case Study: Gob Loading in a Glass Moulding Machine". *Procedia CIRP*. 2016. Pages 203-208. ISSN 2212-8271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2016>.
- [9] J. Chapelin, A. Voisin, B. Rose, B. Iung, L. Steck, L. Chaves, M. Lauer and O. Jotz. "Data-driven drift detection and diagnosis framework for predictive maintenance of heterogeneous production processes: Application to a multiple tapping process". *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*. Vole 139. Part A. 2025.
- [10] V. Kapp, M. C. May, G. Lanza, and T. Wuest. "Pattern Recognition in Multivariate Time Series: Towards an Automated Event Detection Method for Smart Manufacturing Systems". *Journal of Manufacturing and Materials Processing*. Vol 4. doi: 10.3390/jmmp4030088. 2020.
- [11] K. Miroslav, A. Pilipović, and N. Stefanic. "Improving the quality of glass containers production with plunger process control". *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*. Vol 3. 2011.
- [12] M. Cattaldo, A. Ferrer, and I. Mâge. "Variable time delay estimation in continuous industrial processes". *Chemometrics and Intelligent Laboratory Systems*. ISSN 0169-7439. 2024.
- [13] "OpenZDM Project". Accessed: April, 1, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://www.openzdm.eu/>
- [14] M. G. Kendall. "A New Measure of Rank Correlation". *Biometrika*. 1938.
- [15] C. Spearman. "The Proof and Measurement of Association between Two Things". *The American Journal of Psychology*. 1904.
- [16] K. Pearson. "Note on Regression and Inheritance in the Case of Two Parents. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London*". 1895.
- [17] Glass Manufacturing Process Dataset – Gob Variables and Final Thickness. Accessed: June, 17, 2025. [Online.] Available: <https://zenodo.org/records/15679950>